

Questionnaire for participants of the study on: Auditory neuro-feedback systems for biomedical applications (POST experiment)

During synchronization experiment #X:

1. Please indicate the picture below which best describes your relationship with your partner during this musical interaction.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7
0	0	0	0	0	0	0

2. To what extent did you feel “agency” over the musical performance? (Feelings of agency are described as having a subjective feeling of control. In other words, agency is feeling a general sense of control over what you are doing or over the situation you are in.)

Not at all			Partly			Very Much
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
0	0	0	0	0	0	0

3. To what extent did you feel “shared agency” over the musical performance? (When two or more people partake in something together, they can feel a sense of shared agency over what they are doing or the situation they are in. When you feel this shared agency, you feel as if you are going something together (your experience is the product of something done together). When you do not feel shared agency, you feel as if others did not have any control over your experience, and that you acted completely independently.)

Not at all			Partly			Very Much
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
0	0	0	0	0	0	0

3. How do you rate the last performance?

Not good			Neutral			Very good
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
0	0	0	0	0	0	0

4. Place yourself back in the activity and indicate the most appropriate category.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
	Not at all			Partly			Very much
I feel just the right amount of challenge	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
I am totally absorbed in what I am doing	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
My thoughts/activities run fluidly and smoothly	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
I have no difficulty concentrating	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
The right thoughts/movements occur of their own accord	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

5. Please rate the last activity in terms of **BOTH sliders** (their order of appearance will be changed randomly).

Pleasure ranging from unpleasant to pleasant. Arousal ranging from calm to excited.

Move the slider to rate your level of Pleasure

Move the slider to rate your level of Arousal